

The Delay and Failure of ICT Related Projects: Empirical Impediments in Ministries, Departments and Agencies in Tanzania

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Abstract:

This study investigates impediments to ICT project success in MDAs in Tanzania. The study is carried using descriptive design and is carried in Dodoma and Dar es salaam with five big organizations implementing ICT projects which acted as representative of the rest. Such organizations include Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), TAMISEMI, Electronic Government Agency (eGA), Tanzania Ports Authority (TPA) and Tanzania Medicines and Medical Devices Authority (TMDA). Data is collected through the use of questionnaire and analysed descriptively by the use of IBM SPSS version 20. Findings disclose that presence of inadequate staff with limited skilled, lack of up to date and supporting ICT infrastructure

coupled with limited financial resources lead to ICT project failure. Based on these findings, the researcher concludes that, adequate skilled staff availed with the required facilities and funded effectively lead to ICT project success or otherwise. It is therefore recommended that meritocratic staffing be implemented but still on-job trainings should be emphasized as well. In the same vein, the researcher recommends the government to set sufficient budget to obtain the required ICT equipment for better project performance.

Keywords: *ICT project, Project implementation, competence and skills, ICT infrastructure.*

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is greatly becoming a focal point in changing business undertakings in the world today. As a result of ICT, business have become perfectly competitive and gained super profits in comparison to their rivals (Ebad, 2018). Following this situation, many businesses since the early 1990s started adopting the use of ICT in their business operations. Studies by a number

of scholars (Lawrence & Tar, 2018; Yunis et al., 2018; Albar & Hoque, 2019; Attaran & Woods, 2019) report that businesses that started adoption simple ICT applications in business have currently adopted complex applications and some have completely automated their businesses in terms of planning, execution and data storage. These scholars further report that some businesses are re-engineering their operation processes in order to enjoy full advantage of ICT in their businesses.

While businesses have been changing their operations to fit in the changing world driven by greater changes in the use of ICT, governments around the world have not remained back. In the process of changing processes and procedures have established several projects to ensure that most of their operations are controlled by the use of ICTs both in normal and sensitive ministries and agencies. For instance, in the USA, NASA, CIA and FBI were the first to embrace the use of ICTs and changed a lot of their operations to be computer based. A study by Weber and Kaufmann (2011) presented that in the US only, more than 3.5 trillion USD were spent in acquisition and implementation of ICT projects and the figure was expected to be fourth as much by 2020. In Saudi Arabia, by 2015, the government invested more than 18 Saudi Riyal (SAR) to improve its ICT investment and upgrade its procedures and processes to become ICT compatible (AlBar & Hoque, 2017). In China, massive investments and campaigns were made to ensure that ICT take lead in all government lines. Through the three Golden projects where the golden card, e-government, marked the beginning of total ICT operations in public and private operations (Lee et al., 2014). The situations has been the same in different countries.

In order to move abreast with changes resulting from advancement in ICT. Governments around the world have implemented various projects. While some of these projects succeeded, others failed and others were challenged. According to The Standish Group International (2015), a successful project is the one that has been completed on time, on budget, on target, on goal, and delivers value and satisfaction. It was completed in an acceptable average period, executed within the projected budget and satisfies users irrespective of the original scope. Moreover, a challenged project is the one whose completion was beyond the estimated budget, sooner than anticipated, and diverges with the original state. In the same time, impaired and failed projects are those which were cancelled, abandoned and led to unbearable losses.

ICT project failure is not a new phenomenon in

the world. According to Standish Group (2015), while presenting the US experience, it was reported that out of 25,000 software projects assessed 29 percent of ICT related projects were a success, 52 percent were challenged and 19 percent failed. In 2004, the US, Hewlett Packard lost USD 160 million due to imperfections in the development systems (CIO Staff, 2007). Likewise, in 2005 the US Government's Federal Investigation Bureau(FBI) lost more than USD 170 million dedicated to developing the virtual case file (VCF) management system (Afzal, 2014). Moreover, a similar case was reported in Japan where the Toyota car manufacturer recalled back all Prius model cars because of malfunctions in the installed software (Hirsch, 2014). On the same situation, a study by Vaheed et al. (2015) reported that the ICT system meant for the National health Services was abandoned by the UK government and lead to a loss of £10 billion tax payers' money.

As a result, the issue is widespread throughout the world, extending from established to developing to frontier markets. The problem is not specific to any one industry, since errors have been found in a wide range of sectors, including government, education, aviation, postal service, and the military. Initiatives in the field of government information and communication technology (GICT) have a reputation for being extremely delayed and failing to deliver the expected results. According to Wright and Capps (2010), most major Information System (IS) initiatives can surpass their original budgets and deadlines by more than 50 percent and this happens even more often in government than in the private sector.

In the developing countries, it is reported that most ICT related projects have either partially or completely failed (Hua, 2022). A study by Liana et al. (2023a) reveal that poor project management, incompetence of project managers and limited funds. In another study conducted in Malaysia, factors including a poor business case, a lack of clear expected results, unfocused senior management on the project, poor communication, not properly engaging shareholders, conflicts of interest, bias in project evaluation, not seeing the big picture, and an

unseen, narrow-minded decision maker were identified to be the major cause of failure in these projects (Vaheed et al., 2015). In Tanzania, by considering the crucial role played by ICT in enhancing development, both the government and individual organizations have implemented a number of ICT projects. One of these mega projects is the E-government aimed at enhancing efficiency and providing high-quality public services (URT, 2016). However, numerous projects have been classified to be a failure, and some challenged and caused a waste of a great volume of tax payers' money (Samsor, 2021). In comparison however, the projects in private organizations have been classified to do well than those in the public sector (Blaskovics, Maro, Klimko, Happ-Horvath & Csiszárík-Kocsir, 2023; Cordova, Dulan, Galindo, 2014; Obeidat & North, 2014; Tanzania e-Government Strategy, 2013; Bonina & Cordella, 2010).

While there exist research on the rate, prevalence and causes of failure in ICT projects, such studies are from different contexts (Standish Group, 2015; Ashraf, Mohsin, & Khattak, 2010; Vaheed et al. 2015; Liana et al., 2023). In the Tanzanian context, while the study by Liana et al. (2023) that tried to explain factors leading to failure of ICT is available, its major focus was on technology and leadership related factors. This implies that, other factors as mentioned by other studies elsewhere were left out and were not tested at all. Factors related to staff skills and competencies, infrastructural issues, financial and funding support were not studied at all. In this regard, it is difficult to generate a conclusion on only two factors in this phenomenon. While there is continuous prevalence of failure and challenged ICT projects, and the reasons to explain the phenomenon are limited, and there is a need to undertake a study to mine reasons leading to failure, and challenge of ICT projects in Ministries, Departments and Agencies of the Tanzanian government. Specifically, this study intends;

- To investigate the influence of staff competencies on the failure of ICT Projects in MDAs in Tanzania.

- To analyze the effect of availability of infrastructural facilities on the failure of ICT projects in MDAs in Tanzania.
- To assess the influence of availability of financial resources on failure of ICT Projects in MDAs in Tanzania.

Materials and Methods

Research Approach and Design

The study after considering the needs of the research objectives, decided to use the quantitative research approach which includes the description and presentation of the obtained findings in numerical and metric forms like percentages and other forms of statistics (Rahman, 2016). The approach was useful as it provided us with a variety of data collection and analysis approaches as well as thorough examination of hindrances to ICT projects. Moreover, the approach drew the line of association between variables in this study. Following this reality, the descriptive cross-sectional design was used. The approach allowed the researcher to reach a wide range of the population in MDAs.

Population and Sample

The study was conducted in the five sampled MDA whose total population was 860 employees. These were either implementers or directly and indirectly affected by the implementation of such projects in their respective organizations. ICT projects considered in this study included software, networking and security related projects. These included ICT offices, accountants, Procurement staff, and other related staff. Out of this population, a sample of 90 respondents was determined by the use of sampling formula as;

$$n = N$$

$$1 + N(e)^2$$

n - Is the sample size for the study

N- Is the study population

e- Is the level of precision

$N=860$ $e=10\%$

Therefore, n will be = 860

$1+860(0.10)^2$

= 89.583

=90

Following the determination of the sample size, the researchers selected respondents of the study. These were selected by the use of purposive sampling and convenient sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used to sample Project managers, heads of ICT, finance officers, customer service, and human resources departments. These were selected because of their knowledge and direct involvement and use of such ICT related projects. Moreover, convenient sampling was used to sample other respondents including ICT staff, Customer services staff, human resource officers, and accountants. This technique was used following the nature of these organizations and following the impossibility of using simple random sampling the office settings.

Sources and Tools of Data Collection

The study used both primary and secondary sources of data. Primary data, considered as fresh and originally collected from the source were collected by the use of questionnaire. The questionnaire involved questions relating to skills and competencies, infrastructure and funding. These were administered to the sampled respondents through Drop on and Pick Up (DOPU) technique. In this the researcher dropped questionnaires to the sampled respondents and picked them after one day. With regard to secondary data, document review was done. The researcher reviewed published reports, journals and books relating to ICT project implementation. The data obtained from these sources provided more data that complemented the one collected through questionnaire. Before the questionnaire was deployed, it was first tested through a pilot study.

This helped to fix errors, minimize ambiguities and improve the level of dependability of the study. Moreover, to determine their reliability, the Cronbach Alpha was used. As the rule of the thumb, the coefficient closer to 1 means higher level of internal consistence and the opposite is true. The reliability test conducted is presented in Table1

Table 1. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	Value	.812
	N of Items	2 ^a
	Total N of Items	3
Correlation Between Forms		.871
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length	.773
	Unequal Length	.723
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient		.713

Findings reveal that variables scored a value of .812 that translates to reliable variables and thus allowed to be considered for further analysis.

Data Analysis

Researchers in this stage systematically arranged, described, illustrated and summarized findings obtained from the study. The study obtained majority of its data from close ended questionnaire. These were keyed in the SPSS version 26, cleaned, coded and then analyzed descriptively and by the use of inferential statistics. In this study a linear regression analysis was conducted to determine the relationship existing between skills and competence, infrastructure availability, and funding on ICT project failure in MDAs in Tanzania. For clarity, findings obtained from secondary sources were used to complement or contradict the ones obtained from the primary sources.

Results and Discussion

Staff Competence and Failure of ICT Projects in MDAs

This was the first objective of this study. The objective was aimed at generating the relationship existing between staff competence and skills issue and failure of ICT projects. In

order to obtain findings, a number of questions were prepared. These questions focused on the number or staff, skills they have, training, experience and qualifications. These were in form of a seven-point Likert scale where 1=

strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= moderately disagree, 4= neutral, 5= moderately agree, 6= agree, 7= strongly agree. Findings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Responses on Staff Competence and ICT Project Failure

Aspects	SD	D	SLD	N	SLA	A	SA
There are inadequate number of staffs to implement ICT projects.	0%	7%	1%	9%	33%	42%	8%
Staff are not provided with ICT project implementation and general computer training.	1%	7%	8%	12%	27%	33%	12%
Staff are incompetent and inexperienced on ICT project implementation.	5%	14%	6%	9%	20%	31%	15%
Staff are not qualified in ICT usage and project implementation.	4%	9%	1%	6%	21%	48%	11%
Staff have no specialized knowledge and technical skills on ICT project implementation.	3%	10%	4%	11%	37%	25%	10
Staff have limited skills on ICT project supervision.	15%	0%	7%	18%	12%	29%	19%
Staff are not committed to the success of ICT projects.	0%	1%	5%	8%	20%	41%	25%

Key: SD= Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, SLD=Slightly disagree, N=Neutral, SLA= Slightly Agree, A= Agree, SA= Strongly Agree.

Findings in Table 2 indicate that there is a reasonable level of agreement among respondent on regarding the influence of different specific issues on project failure. Findings reveal that 83% agreed on inadequacy of ICT staff, 62% agreed that there are limited trainings on ICT project implementation, 660% agree that staff have limited competence and experience to run ICT projects and 80% agree that staff do not have qualifications of using and implementing such projects. It is moreover recorded that 72% of respondent agreed that staff have limited knowledge and skills of project implementation, 60% agree that there is limited skills on project supervision and 86% agreed that

staff are not committed towards ICT project implementation.

Availability of Infrastructure and ICT Project Failure

This was the second objective of the study. The objective was aimed at linking the availability of infrastructure and ICT project implementation. The researcher expected that in the situation where staff have the required infrastructure, it would be easy for the project to be a success otherwise a failure. The researcher identified several aspects aligned to infrastructure. Based on a seven-point Likert scale questions, its scores are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Response on Infrastructure Availability and ICT Project Failure

Aspects	SD	D	SLD	N	SLA	A	SA
Hardware are poorly available (computers, printers and external storage devices)	0%	2%	0%	6%	27%	41%	24%
Limited connection to networked systems through high speed internet connection	3%	5%	8%	4%	19%	44%	17%
Systems are technically not flexible and not configured to facilitate IT projects	1%	6%	3%	7%	22%	39%	22%
There are only a few IT applications to be used for project implementation	1%	0%	11%	9%	31%	19%	29%

Key: SD= Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, SLD=Slightly disagree, N=Neutral, SLA= Slightly Agree,

A= Agree, SA= Strongly Agree.

Findings in Table 2 indicate that there is a reasonable level of agreement among respondent on regarding the influence of different specific issues on project failure. Findings reveal that 92% agree that there is scarcity of hardware including storage devices, advanced ICT gadgets, and more to allow them implement ICT projects smoothly. Furthermore, 80% of respondents agreed that network connection is limited and sometimes unstable, 83% agreed that systems are technically not flexible to allow smooth implementation of ICT projects. Moreover, regarding the availability of up-to-date applications, 79% agreed that there are only a few IT application that can be used to implement ICT related projects. This being the

case, it can be generalized that infrastructural related issues are a major cause of ICT project failure in MDAs in Tanzania.

Financial Resources and ICT Project Failure

In this objective, the researcher was interested to find out the existing relationship between financial resources and project failure. It was the researchers' expectations that a well-funded project is always successful, otherwise a failure. The finances an organization commits to the project leads to its failure of success. Through the use of several ranking questions, the relationship was determined and findings are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Response on Financial Resources and ICT Project Failure

Aspects	SD	D	SLD	N	SLA	A	SA
There are financial resources for ICT infrastructure setup lead to success	20%	46%	21%	5%	1%	3%	4%
There are financial resources for staffing ICT capable employees	18%	32%	26%	14%	4%	4%	2%
ICT projects are well funded	15%	27%	34%	10%	5%	3%	6%
There is a special and adequate budget for ICT project implementations	26%	49%	12%	3%	0%	9%	1%

Key: SD= Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, SLD=Slightly disagree, N=Neutral, SLA= Slightly Agree, A= Agree, SA= Strongly Agree.

The influence of funds on project implementation cannot be under estimated. Findings in Table 4 indicate that there is a reasonable level of agreement among respondent on regarding the influence of different specific issues on project failure. Findings reveal that 87% disagree on the presence of funds for ICT project setup, 76% disagree that there are designated funds for staffing competent and capable employees, 76% disagree on ICT projects being well funded, and 87% disagree that there is a special and adequate budget for ICT project implementation. This being the case, in the situation where there is no special and adequate budget for ICT project setup, staffing and implementation, it is automatically that the implemented project will be a failure.

Inferential Statistics

Regression analysis

Following the findings obtained as presented in Tables 2,3 and 4, it was clearly shown that there is a relationship between staff competence, infrastructure availability and finance on failure of ICT projects. Researchers wanted to statistically test this relationship. The regression analysis was used to test the relationship. Before the analysis was done, the multicollinearity and correlations among variables were tested. The Variance Inflation and resistance factor (VIF) were used. According to Hair e al. (2010) the VIF above 4.0 and the tolerance value is below 0.2, there is the presence of multicollinearity. Findings of the tests are presented in Table 5.

	Financial factors	.306	3.213
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Table 5. Tolerance and VIF Value for Independent Variables

Model		Collinearity statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
	(Constant)		
	Competence factors	.551	1.808
	Infrastructure factors	.701	1.442

Findings obtained in Table 5 indicate that all variables have a tolerance value of above 0.20. Moreover, the VIF value to all variables did not exceed 4. Such findings suggest that there is no collinearity in the dataset. This implies that each construct present independent and unique information. In this regard therefore, the study was allowed to conduct a regression analysis and the findings are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. The Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimation
1	.843 ^a	.710	.683	.34182

Note: Predictors: (constant), Competence factors, Infrastructure factors, Financial factors.

Findings obtained in this analysis indicate that independent variables strongly predict ICT project failure by 84.3%. Following the values on R square, this indicates that there is a significant variance in the dependent variable. This implies

that competence factors, availability of infrastructures and availability of funds greatly influence the failure of ICT project implementation. The R square is 71% allowing the researcher to proceed with further analysis.

Table 7. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
	Regression	16.238	7	2.318	23.322	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.432	56	.133		
	Total	23.67	63			
a. Dependent variables: Factors for ICT project failure						
b. Predictors: (constant), Competence factors, Infrastructure factors, Finance factors						

The ANOVA findings as presented in Table 7 indicate that out of the variance of 23.67, independent variables are responsible for 16.238 and the remaining 7.432 being factors beyond the realm of the study's model. This

indicates that independent variables have explanator power in this study's model that explains ICT project failure. Further the regression coefficient obtained are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Regression Analysis-Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.872	.338		2.134	.032
	Competence factors	.024	.072	.026	.331	.000
	Infrastructure factors	.086	.112	.074	.661	.002
	Finance factors	.123	.091	.141	1.663	.004

Findings presented in Table 8 indicate that Competence factor ($\beta= 0.026$, $p= .000$), infrastructure factors ($\beta=0.074$, $p=0.002$), finance factors ($\beta= 0.141$, $p=0.004$). All factors have statistically significant relationship with ICT project failure in MDAs in Tanzania. Such variables demonstrate the presence of positive relationship between these variables and project failure. The regression analysis provides that, while considering factors impeding the successful implementation of ICT projects in MDAs in Tanzania, it is important to consider competence factors, infrastructure factors as well as financial factors.

These findings are in line with a number of studies presented by previous studies. For instance, with regard to competence factors, findings indicate that, for every decrease in component of staff competence, there is an increase in the ICT project failure. According to Cooke-Davies (1997) the failure of ICT projects depends on staff competence and skills. Contributing to this, Kuen (2009) reported that the future success of ICT projects depends on competence otherwise total failure. Moreover, Njuru (2011) and Lubua and Maharaj (2012) emphasize on trainings as a means of improving and re-shaping their competence and skills without which leads to failure of these projects. In the same vein, Tsui (1997) notes that the presence of skills coupled with commitment leads to projects success however, lack of which greatly leads to project failure.

With regard to infrastructure factors, findings reveal that they contribute heavily to failure of ICP projects. Such findings are in line with a number of scholars whose opinions are similar to these findings. For instance, a study by Njuru (2011) and Lubua and Maharaj (2012) report that in the presence of the right infrastructure such as hard ware, fibre networks lead to success. However, lack of these, lead to project failure. In another study Asgarkhani et al. (2017) unveils that the lack of up-to date applications, data,

connectivity and technical configurations lead to IT project failure. Moreover, Syed et al. (2016) reports that with limited infrastructures ICT project implementation might be a failure.

With respect to financial factors, it has been reported that limited funds lead to failure in ICT project implementation. This is similar to other previous studies which presented similar findings. For instance, a study by Ndayisaba and Mulyungi (2018) revealed that there is a great relationship between limited financial resources and ICT project failure. Similar to these, Gomes and Romao (2016) confirm that in the absence of financial resources ICT project re prone to failure. Supporting this view, Volden, (2018), Kissi, et al. (2019), point that with limited financial resources there is a great chance of failure of ICT projects. The findings were further supported by Iriarte and Bayona (2020) who mentioned among other factors that lead to ICT project failure, labour, plants and other financial resources lead to the failure of ICT projects. Similarly, Wright and Capps (2010) reveals that although organizations set special budgets, in most cases the ICT projects normally surpass the allocated budgets and that is the reason as to why some projects never succeed.

Conclusion

In this study, it was established that a project with inadequate staffs with limited skill and techniques in ICT and project management have a great contribution to the failure of ICT projects in MDAs. It is revealed that, if the project is deployed without qualified staff to implement, supervise and use the project, the outcome would always be a failure of that project.

Moreover, because the study revealed that lack of the required infrastructure lead to project failure, therefore the presence of the required equipment including soft and hard wares, up-to-

date applications, flexible and configured systems may lead to project success.

With regards to finance resources, the study concludes that the adequate allocation of funds to ICT projects will change the situation. It is through such finance that competent staff are employed, money to procure necessary equipment is obtained and funds for the real implementation of such projects is rooted. Therefore, an organization that is short of financial resources is likely to fail implementing ICT projects at all.

The study proposes several strategies to ensure that ICT projects are successfully implemented. MDAs are urged to employ qualified IT project managers through meritocratic employment systems. The study further proposes the provision of periodic on-job training to ICT staff and project implementers. This improves their skills and lowers the rate of failures in implementing ICT projects. The study urges MDAs to allocate adequate budget and disburse the money in time. This will allow projects to deploy the required infrastructure, but still buy the required resources in time.

While this study only focused on public organization, because in different settings, its findings can be done focusing on private organizations. But also, more factors should be added to the model.

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